

Antecedent of Boko – Haram Insurgence in Northern Nigeria: Implications on Property Investment Returns

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Abstract: *Whenever and wherever the radical Boko Haram sect operates within and across the border of Nigeria, it often leaves behind pathetic stories and frightening scenes of destruction of lives and properties. The study reviews the implications of Boko Haram insurgence on property investment returns in Northern Nigeria. The study is descriptive and data was retrieved from both published and unpublished sources. It was established that the heinous activities of the sect over time have forced occupiers or users of different classes of investment properties to relocate their businesses and residences from the crisis-ridden areas in northern Nigeria to towns and cities that are of less or no crisis. Property investors in crisis-ridden areas are counting losses as a result of the displacement and relocation of users or occupiers who pay rents in consideration for use. When property investment returns are at a halt, investors' financial obligations will not be met. In a bid to curb the menace of the insurgence for economic stability in general and to harness property investment returns in particular, the study recommends amongst others that the Nigeria government should desist from promoting the Almajiri's school system in northern Nigeria but rather promote free western education that guarantees career employability potentials by incorporating the Almajiris into the existing public-operated schools. It is not gainsaying that the Almajiris are tutored and brainwashed with mindless extremism and radicalism as a result of poverty and homelessness. When these Almajiris eventually graduate, they would become radical and threat to lives and properties.*

Keywords: Boko – Haram, Insurgence, Northern – Nigeria, Property investment returns

1. Introduction

Property investment involves the commitment of capital sum for the acquisition of interest in real properties in anticipation of future benefits. According to Olayonwa (2012), if the benefits are measured in monetary terms, they may be in the form of annual income if rented or profit if sold. Investment properties are capable of generating income or yielding returns through renting, leasing or price appreciation, and their capital values are best determined by their income potential. Property investment is the preoccupation of both the public and private sectors. The public sector direct investment in real property might not necessarily be for economic returns compared with the private sector counterparts whose motive is to

maximize returns. Both sectors leverage the demand for various property types triggered by urbanization towards attaining their investment motives.

In the opinion of Ogungbemi (2012) and Onatu (2009), the persistent increase in property investment is attributed to the rapid pace of urbanization, and according to UN-Habitat (2011), urbanization has made rental property investment an important option for meeting with various real property demands of the urban dwellers that may not have the capital requirements to buy or develop properties of their own. Simecek (2006) and Langsether, Gulbrandsen, and Annaniassen (2003) opined that rental property investment emerged as a partial solution to urbanization. In the world all over, real estate investors and users are leveraging urbanization to develop and use investment properties flexibly to maximize returns and satisfy their accommodation needs.

Nigeria, a country in the West African sub-region, has a virile property market. The market is a conglomerate of sub-markets which operate in different geographical locations with the principal aim of bringing the grantor and grantee; assignor and assignee; and lessor and lessee of interest in land and landed property in close contact. The motive of most investors in the Nigerian property market is to maximize returns from real property by renting it out to short-term or long-term tenants for a periodic payment known as rent. In some parts of the country, the motive of maximizing returns from property investment might be an ordinary mirage as a result of the Boko Haram intermediate insurgency that characterized the country in recent times.

According to Meehan and Spaier (2011), Boko Haram is an extremely violent Islamic movement known as “Jama’atul Alhul Sunnah Lidda’ Wat, Wal Jihad” meaning a group committed to the propagation of Prophet Muhammed’s teachings and Jihad. This group has perpetrated several bombings that have killed several innocent Nigerians and foreign nationals and left both public and private properties worth billions of naira destroyed. The continued bombings, maimings, killings, abductions and the destruction of property by the sect threaten national security and socio-economic activities. These nefarious activities are crimes against Nigeria State. In the opinion of Alao, Atere, and Alao (2012), the Boko Haram insurgency has slowed down the national economic growth and development since no investors would prefer to invest in a crisis-ridden nation. The scourge of the sect ushered inestimable damage to every facet of life in Nigeria and has put the country in the news for quite some time, unfortunately for a somewhat negative reason.

Several studies have been conducted on the implications of Boko haram antecedents in Nigeria. A few of these studies were Muraina, Iyanga, and Muraina (2014) on implications on educational development; Aduloju, Opanike, and Adenipekun (2014) on implications on security and stability; Ezema (2013); Awojobi (2014); Mohammed (2014) on implications on socio-economic activities. None of these studies particularly considered the implications of the nefarious activities of the Boko haram sect on property investment returns in Nigeria. However, this study reviewed the antecedents of the Boko haram insurgency in Nigeria and its implications on property investment returns intending to make a policy recommendation that would assist policymakers on ways to curb the menace of insurgency for economic stability in general and to harness property investment returns in particular.

2. Boko Haram Insurgence in Nigeria

Nigeria is a multi-ethnicity country in the West Africa region with a land mass measuring approximately 923,768 square kilometres. It borders the Republic of Benin to the West; Cameroon to the East; the Gulf of Guinea to the South; and the Chad Republic to the North. Nigeria became an independent nation in 1960 after several years of colonial rule and attained Republic in 1963. The country's population was approximately 167 million and still growing at the rate of 2.3% per annum (Olokor, 2012).

Fig. 1: Map of Nigeria showing Attacked States in Northern Nigeria

Source: Adapted from Vox (2014)

Since the attainment of her independence in 1960, Nigerians have been faced with a myriad of problems emanating from disorderliness, mismanagement, and the latest insecurity development. The spate of her insecurity in recent times has drawn attention not only from academia but also in everyday discussion. Nigeria, an Africa-continental power and the main peacekeeper in some conflict-torn states in West Africa and beyond, is currently being terrorized by the Boko Haram sect on its soil with grave consequences for Africa and the international community.

Boko Haram is the unofficial name for the Islamic fundamentalist sect that began to terrorize Nigeria in recent times. According to Meehan and Spaier (2011); Okpaga, Chijioke and Eme (2012), Boko Haram is an extremely violent Islamic movement known as “Jama’atul Alhul Sunnah Lidda’ Wat, Wal Jihad” meaning a group committed to the propagation of Prophet Muhammed’s teachings and Jihad. According to Sanni (2011), “Boko-Haram” was derived from Hausa and Arabic words. “Boko” in Hausa means “Western education” and “Haram” an Arabic word means “sin”. Literarily, Boko Haram means “Western education is forbidden” which is the belief the sect emphasized to have a corrupting influence on traditional values, beliefs and customs amongst Muslim communities in Northern Nigeria.

Numerous expositions on the origin and founder of Boko Haram abound in literature. Some scholars established that the sect began as a Sahaba group in 1995 under the leadership of Lawan Abubakar while others posited that the Sahaba group was under the leadership of Shehu Sanni, a civil rights activist in Northern Nigeria. According to Shehu (2012), when Lawan Abubakar left Nigeria for the University of Medina in Saudi Arabia in quest for knowledge, Muhammed Yusuf took over the affairs of the group. Immediately Muhammed Yusuf took over the leadership of the group, the doctrine of the sect changed and he abandoned the older cleric view and came up with extremist Boko Haram doctrine. Although, he started as an indigenous Salafist group in 2002 in the city of Maiduguri to establish a Sharia government in the twelve northern states of Nigeria, eventually, spreading to the rest of the country. According to Shehu (2012), by 2009, the Salafist group turned out to be a Salafist jihadist group terrorizing the peace and security of Nigeria. From its inception, Boko Haram viewed Nigeria as a state or a country run by non-believers and made the government its main target, even when the country had a Muslim president.

In the opinion of Eme and Ibietan (2012), the ideology of the sect is to bring to an end the secular system of government and introduce sharia law in Nigeria. However, Lister (2012)

had a contrary opinion that the sects are disgruntled youths who have been paid by unscrupulous Northern politicians to cause mayhem in the country because of their selfish ambitions. Moreover, the contrary opinion of the southerners is that the activities of the sect were more intensified because of the emergence of the current president from the south-south region.

Ajah (2011) and Dibia (2012) opined that the extra-judicial killing of the sect leader (Muhammed Yusuf) and some of his cohorts somewhere in the northern part of Nigeria has made the group intensify its attacks on government departments and facilities, churches, media organizations, markets, homes, police and military formations. Awojobi (2014) stated that it is erroneous to believe that the sect attacks churches without doing the same to the Muslim worshipping centres. Boko Haram has attacked mosques in the northeast and even killed some Islamic clerics who are opposed to their ideology.

After the extra-judicial killing of Muhammed Yusuf, Abubakar Shekau who was his deputy took over the mantle of leadership. With the personality of Abubakar Shekau, the sect became more violent and their attacks became more destructive. As observed by Fawole (2013), the sect becomes the most feared terrorist group in the history of Nigeria today, having a transnational reach into neighbouring countries of Cameroon, Chad, Niger and possibly, Mali.

Since 2009, the sect has grown to become a serious national, regional and international concern which attracted the first major international attention in August 2011 when it bombed the United Nations Building in Abuja, killing 23 people. It has sustained its insurgency in Nigeria since then and has even increased its violent attacks and activities in the Northeastern states of Nigeria in 2014. For instance, 2014 has been the worst period of the group attacks. Thousands of people have been killed in attacks on 40 villages in the northeast states of Borno, Yobe and Adamawa. Most of the attacks are concentrated in these three states. However, the nation's capital Abuja, Jos, Kano and some parts of the north have experienced attacks from Boko Haram. Moreover, the sect drew unprecedented international attention when it kidnapped over 200 schoolgirls in Chibok, Borno State, Nigeria in April 2014, which triggered the international campaign "Bring Back Our Girls". Meanwhile, the Islamic fundamentalist group has continued killings, pillages, abductions and bombings at different locations in North-East, North-West, and North-Central of Nigeria.

In the opinions of Cook (2013); Awojobi (2014); Onuoha (2014), the prevalence of poverty, unemployment and political corruption have been blamed on enlistment of youths into the Boko Haram group. It was established in literature that most of the foot soldiers of Boko Haram are youths who are frustrated because of the lack of employment, and income and they have been disdained by politicians after being used by these politicians for their election victory. Whenever and wherever the sect operates, it often leaves behind sad stories and scary scenes of destruction, maiming and death (Jams Bwala, 2011). To curtail the heinous crime of the sect against humanity, the federal government of Nigeria in 2013 declared a state of emergency in the three states where the sect activities predominate. The state of emergency did not stop the sect from the continuation of bombings, killings, kidnappings and the destruction of property. Meanwhile, the attacks of the sect in the period of state of emergency surpassed when there was no state of emergency. The Islamic fundamentalist group as observed by Muraina et al. (2014), have killed the rich and the poor, young and old, males and females, weak and strong, elites and commoners, northerners and southerners alike. With this, it can be reasonably concluded that the Boko Haram insurgency is a war against Nigeria state. Table 1 illustrates some of the series of Boko Haram attacks and fatalities.

Table 1: Some of the series of Boko Haram Attacks in Northern Nigeria that made Local and International Headlines

S/N	Date	State	Types of Attack	Fatalities
1.	18 June 16, 2011	FCT	Bomb explosion at the Nigerian Police Headquarters in Abuja	3 people were killed and several vehicles damaged
2.	28 August 26, 2011	FCT	Bomb explosion at the United Nations Building in Abuja	25 people were killed and over 60 people injured
3.	25 December, 2011	Niger	Bomb explosion at a Catholic Church in Madalla on Christmas Day mass	Over 50 people died and several injured
4.	20 January, 2012	Kano	Multiple attacks in the Kano metropolis	About 250 people were killed and several injured
5.	15 February, 2012	Kogi	Jail break in Koton Karji Prisons	A prison warder was killed and 199 prisoners serving different jail terms were released
6.	17 June, 2012	Kaduna	Multiple bomb attacks on 3 churches	About 70 people were killed and injured scores of others
7.	29 September, 2013	Yobe	Attack on sleeping students of the College of Agriculture, Guijba	50 students were killed and over 150 sustained injuries

Contd.

S/N	Date	State	Types of Attack	Fatalities
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8.	6 July, 2013	Yobe	Attack on students of Government Secondary School, Mamudo	41 students and 1 teacher killed
9.	15 February, 2014	Bornu	Attack on the Christian Village of Izghe	Over 100 people were killed and several injured
10.	14 April, 2014	Bornu	Attack on Government Secondary School, Chibok	276 school girls writing WASSCE were kidnapped
11.	14 April, 2014	FCT	Bomb explosion at Nyanya Motor Park	Over 75 persons were killed and several injured
12.	1 May, 2014	FCT	Bomb explosion at Nyanya Motor Park	19 persons were killed and over 80 people injured
13.	5 May, 2014	Bornu	Attack on Gamboru Ngala Town	At least 300 people were killed while the town was destroyed
14.	20 May, 2014	Plateau	Bomb explosion at Jos market	118 were feared dead and over 56 were injured
15.	7 January, 2015	Bornu	Massacre in Baga town and its environ	Over 2000 people were killed or unaccounted for and over 35,000 people displaced

Source: Author's Compilation (2015)

3. Qualities, Choices and Returns Determinants of Property Investment

Investment generally, is an expenditure of an existing capital sum in anticipation of future benefits. In the opinion of Olayonwa (2012), if the benefits are measured in monetary terms they may be in the form of annual income if the investment is retained; or profit on the sale of such investment. According to Udechukwu (2009), investment is the giving up of a capital sum in return for an income or benefit to be received periodically. The benefit may be in monetary or non-monetary form. Kuye (2000) posited that it is the use of an indirect process to obtain a higher output. The indirect process may involve the saving or expanding of capital to obtain higher productivity which may be in the form of increased output, improved production methods or replacing obsolete equipment.

Property investment, in particular, comprises land, land and buildings, plant and machinery attached thereto for production purposes or purposes. Direct investment in real property involves the acquisition of an interest in land, land and buildings to receive annual returns in the form of rent or a capital gain on the outright sale of the property.

Property investment is considered an ideal investment because of the multifarious qualities it possesses. These qualities as observed by Olayonwa (2012); Udechukwu (2009); Kuye (2000), offer the security of capital because of the indestructible nature of the land. This is the most important feature because the majority of investors will want to invest their money in investments that promise/assure the recoupment of capital at any point in time should the

need arise even though there is no profit. Although property investment is a victim of unforeseen events like fire outbreaks, storms, earthquakes etc., the capital is secured through mitigating the unforeseen events by taking insurance cover. By this, the investor is guaranteed the return on capital invested at any time when the need for the sale arises.

Furthermore, property investment appreciates over time, therefore, the investor is guaranteed the return of capital invested at any time when the need for sale arises without any loss. Furthermore, income from property investment is regular and certain compared to other investment alternatives. For instance, in a tenanted property, the tenants would certainly pay rent to the landlords on or before the expiration of their tenancies by effluxion of time. Income from this kind of investment is certain and regular. Moreover, property investment can produce certain returns over time. As a result of the certainty and regularity of its income, the income from the investment is secured against future inflation that cripples the purchasing power of money. Also, property investment has tax advantages especially when the premium is received by the landlord from his tenant. The tax liability on the lump sum received by the landlord may be low if the rate of tax chargeable on income tax is greater than that of capital gains. In addition, property investment is perhaps one of the best available collateral for a loan facility. The reasons for this cannot be over-emphasized because the landed property has some special characteristics such as a hedge against inflation, confers prestige on the owner, can easily be sold especially at forced sale value etc., all making landed property a good choice of investment. Lastly, property investment lasts for many years with a very slow rate of deterioration (coupled with management efficiency), even when the property is old and the rate of deterioration has quickened, the value of the land will continue to increase. Because of the durable nature of the land, investors are compelled to spend money on its maintenance and improvement. This is done to sustain and possibly increase the value of the property throughout its economic life. The reason why this is done is because investors are confident that they will get their money's worth over the long life of the property. In addition, property investment can be easily converted into cash with ease if need be through sale.

Meanwhile, investors in real property have a wide range of choices of the type of property to invest their capital on. The types of property vary which are residential, commercial, industrial, agricultural, recreational and institutional property investments (Udechukwu, 2009; Olayonwa, 2012; Corcoran, 1987; Galaty, Allaway, and Kyle, 2000). The returns from investment properties are largely influenced by the physical characteristics and economic conditions of the market. The physical characteristics include design, accommodation details,

services, facilities, neighbourhood, location, accessibility, adjoining properties, state of repairs and government legislation. On the other hand, the economic conditions of the market are the forces of demand and supply, cost of construction, availability or non-availability of substitutes etc. Globally, the certainty and regularity of returns that property investments assure those who invested in it and other outstanding qualities it possesses give it an edge over other investment media.

4. Risk Posed by Boko Haram Insurgence on Property Investment in Northern Nigeria

In everyday usage, risk is used to denote exposure to danger, adversity or loss. Okoh (2008) posited that risk is the uncertainty of the occurrence of unfavourable outcomes. Odeyomi (2007) opined that it is the possibility of losing return and/or capital invested in a project. According to Olayonwa (2012), risk is a situation where the actual investment outcome differs from the expected outcome. Risks associated with property investment returns are diversified. These risks are broadly classified into financial risk; business risk; tenant risk; purchasing power risk; liquidity risk; structural risk; market risk, interest rate risk; legislation/social or regulatory risk; and political environment risk.

From the myriad of risks associated with property investment, the internal crisis of Boko Haram in Nigeria posed a market risk on investment properties. Market risk relates to the happenings in the local and national economy. This is the risk that arises from factors that are external to the investment. The causes of changes in market value are usually beyond the control of the investor. For instance, there may be an unexpected war in the area which might negatively affect the performance of the property market of the area i.e. the risk will be high. Moreover, it may be an election year where so much cash is injected into the economy which might increase the demand for properties in the area i.e. the market risk for that area will be reduced.

The Boko Haram insurgence is an internal war against Nigeria state by the fundamentalist sect since 2009 till date. Their nefarious activities since inception posed a high market risk in Nigeria's property market at large and in northern Nigeria's property market in particular. Plates 1 and 2 illustrate market risk that affects property investment returns.

Plate 1: Picture showing devastated property investment (Monday Market), Maiduguri
Source: Adapted from the Nigeria News Day (2015)

Plate 2: Picture showing devastated property investment (Banex Plaza) at Wuse 2, Abuja
Source: Adapted from the Nigeria News Day (2015)

5. Implications of the Boko Haram Nefarious Activities on Property Investment Returns

Nigeria has long been terrorized by Boko Haram insurgency which has impacted her social, economic and political structures with the property market not spared. The property market of Northeastern Nigeria is experiencing a recession as a result of insurgency. According to BusinessDay, real estate investors have lost investment appetite since the property market remains the major victim of the insurgency putting vacancy rates as high as 30 percent in Yobe, Adamawa, Borno, Katsina and Kano. Moreover, in the opinion of Akinloye (2014), property values have fallen by 30 – 40 percent as a result of low demand. According to Adegbola (2015), a property with an annual return of ₦1,000,000 in 2008 (before the

conflict) fell to ₦600,000 by 2009 – 2013 (conflict period) and still falling. The implications of the nefarious activities of Boko Haram insurgence on property investment returns are overwhelming and cannot be over-emphasized. Different classes of investment properties yielding returns to investors have been attacked by the fundamentalist sect and by implication put business and clerical activities on the affected properties and unaffected contiguous ones at a halt.

Some of the users or occupiers of commercial property investment have lost their lives in the process while others who escaped death have relocated their businesses to towns and cities with less or no crisis (Yakubu, 2012). Users and occupiers of these properties if not dead by heinous attacks of Boko haram are fast relocating as a result of their investment mobility while investors of the commercial property investments cannot withdraw or relocate them from crisis-ridden areas to towns and cities that are of less or no crisis as a result of the fixity of landed property. For instance, tenants in various property investments can relocate their businesses from Maiduguri to Lagos while investors of these properties cannot withdraw their investment properties from Maiduguri for relocation to Lagos or other crisis-free states. The returns from these properties would cease as a result of economic and functional obsolescence triggered by the activities of the fundamentalist sect. Tenants in shops (lock-ups and stalls) that are not attacked by the sect in the troubled northeastern states have been forced by military personnel to relocate for security reasons. Some of these shops have been taken over by the military operatives who have made it their base, forcing business owners to either relocate or abandon them totally (Mohammed, 2014). Small businesses as observed by Mohammed (2014) that operate at night like Tea selling, Restaurants, suya spots e.t.c. are no longer operating as a result of the security situation. These investment properties would yield no returns to the investors since it has been taken over by the military as the base to tackle the insurgence.

Furthermore, residential property investment in territories taken over by the fundamentalist sect is no longer yielding expected returns to investors since residents have fled to non-troubled towns and cities. Investors in these territories are counting losses since capital invested is tied down at a particular location without yielding expected returns. Investment properties developed for educational purposes in the crisis-ridden areas are no longer bringing returns to investors since students have been forced out of schools as a result of the insurgence. In the opinion of Muraina et al. (2014) More than 800 school buildings (private and public operated) are affected in the north. Moreover, Oladunjoye and Omemu (2013)

observed that school attendance is affected in areas prone to Boko Haram attacks in Northern Nigeria. Parents are sending their wards to study outside the troubled areas as a result of the bloody campaign of the sect on innocent citizenry not even sparing school pupils. Since the inception of Boko Haram, many schools have been attacked, pupils killed, and some abducted while others are left with different degrees of injuries. These heinous activities of the sect have forced children out of schools leaving the institutional investment property physically, functionally and economically obsolete.

The recreational property investments meant for relaxation purposes such as hotels, gym centres, game houses, golf courses, and recreational parks are experiencing low patronage as a result of a bloody campaign of mindless extremists. The activities of the Boko Haram in Northern Nigeria have led to palpable fear among the citizenry in visiting and patronizing recreational properties which by implication dwindled returns from this class of property investment. The returns from this investment type are largely influenced by the magnitude of patronage i.e. the higher the level of patronage, the higher the returns to those who invested in it. Investors in this category of investment are counting losses as a result of residents' indisposition to visit public places and recreational facilities orchestrated by insecurity in northern Nigeria. Moreover, northern Nigeria is widely known for agricultural productivity. This encouraged investors to embrace agricultural property investment in anticipation of returns. Kimenyi, Adibe, Djire, Jirgi, Kergna, Deressa, Pugliese, and Westbury (2014) ascertained that farmers in Borno State experienced large drops in their average production of some farm products, from before the insurgence in the period of 2004 – 2008 to the period during the insurgence, 2009 – 2013. In the study of Kimenyi et al (2014) four hypothetical farmers were interviewed, and the farmers posited that between 2004 – 2008, their farm produced such as cowpea, maize, sorghum, rice and millet with a typical harvest of 3.0, 22.6, 20.8, 3.0 and 5.0 metric tons respectively before the insurgence declined to 0.8, 3.6, 6.4, 1.5 and 1.1 metric tons respectively between 2009 – 2013 (insurgence periods) which dwindled expected returns from agricultural lands. The farmers attributed the decline to the threat of attacks on their way to their farms which made most farmers migrate to villages and towns with less or no crisis.

According to Alao et al. (2012), most migrants from the north are in their productive age and have abandoned the farming profession thereby compounding the problem of food importation. By implication, farmers that use agricultural lands and buildings for the cultivation of crops and rearing of domestic and domesticated animals and pay rent in

consideration for use have neglected farming activities in the crisis-ridden areas resulting in food insecurity in Nigeria at large. Agricultural property Investors are losing returns from their investments because the activities of the sect have forced farmers to down-tools and relocate to other areas thereby resulting in dwindling returns to those who have invested in it.

6. Conclusion

The bloody campaign of the fundamentalist sect has resulted in the death of the rich and poor, citizens and aliens, men and women, boys and girls, and military and para-military personnel, old and young alike. The implications of the insurgence on property investment returns cannot be over-emphasized. Property investors in crisis-ridden areas are counting losses as a result of displacement and relocation of users or occupiers who pay rents in consideration for use. Property investment is an ideal investment because of the certainty and regularity of its returns over time. The heinous activities of the Boko Haram sect have made most investors' motive to maximize returns an ordinary mirage. When investment properties are not capable of yielding returns to the investors, by implication, the investors, most especially those that might have no other source of income would not be able to meet their financial obligations i.e. immediate and future needs of their families, amortization of mortgage facility, maintenance of the investment properties and statutory obligation to the government (taxation).

7. Recommendations

Whenever and wherever the sect operates, it often leaves behind pathetic stories and frightening scenes of destruction of lives and properties. The bloody campaign of the fundamentalist sect has resulted in the death of innocent Nigerians and foreign nationals and has put property investment returns at a halt. To curb the menace of Boko Haram insurgence in Nigeria requires a multi-dimensional approach. Having examined the antecedent of the Boko Haram insurgency in Nigeria and its implications on property investment returns, the study hereby puts forward the following recommendations:

1. The immediate past president of the Federal Republic of Nigeria once posited that sponsors of the radical sect were in his government without making a concerted effort to expose them. The present administration should investigate and expose the sponsors of the sect whose most Nigerians believe are men of teems and calibres in the society, and the government should not hesitate to bring them to justice.

2. The government should equip the military and the joint task force at large with sophisticated and state-of-the-art ammunition and also train and re-train them to wage war against terrorism in Nigeria.
3. Nigerian government should deploy sophisticated technology to detect the hideouts of the sect to arrest and bring them to justice.
4. The heinous activities of the sect are not only a threat to national security but also a threat to global security. Meanwhile, the international community should not cause harm but corroborate with the Nigerian government to ensure that peace is restored to Nigerian territory and other neighbouring countries that are affected by the insurgency.
5. Nigeria citizens should assist the government in exposing the radical fundamentalist sect members that reside amongst them in various cities, towns, villages, hamlets etc. The menace can be curbed if the citizens see the war against terrorism as a collective responsibility.
6. The government should desist from promoting the Almajiri school system in northern Nigeria and rather promote free Western education that guarantees career employability potential. It is strongly believed that pupils of the Almajiri schools are brainwashed with extremism and radicalism as a result of poverty. When these students eventually graduate, they will become radical and treat peace in any environment they might find themselves.
7. As a matter of urgency, the Nigerian government should arrest unemployment ravaging the country. The non-employability of a larger percentage of Nigerian youths is forcing them into crimes ranging from armed robbery, rape, abduction to terrorism. The present administration in collaboration with the private sector should work assiduously to ensure that youths are gainfully employed.
8. To cap it all, the corrupt practices and impunity amongst government functionaries also encourage terrorism. Government should not hesitate to tackle corruption and also ensure that politicians at all levels of government are accountable to their constituents.

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